

Reaction of rice germplasm material to the local isolate of BB pathogen, Faizabad, U. P. India, 1985 and 1986.

Germplasm material	Reaction score ^a	Varieties (no.) with similar score
IET6155	2	1
IET4555, NP085, RP419, Pant Dhan 4, NDU7, NDU22, T63, M23, H62, IET4141	3	10
IET8675, Restonoorin 21-9, T43, W1278, RR51-1, NDR88	4	6
NDR80, NDR84, NDR97, Saket 4, Type 3, CH45, CH1059, HDLL 39, NDU21, NDU37, NDU39, NDU48, SLO-17, SRA41, IET6238, Basmati 370, Pankaj, Ranikazal, Chainphool, Kalakand	5	20
Narendra 1, Narendra 2, NDR308, China 4, Champa coarse, Rohini 1708, K333, CH1039, IET9782, FS18, CR1416, T6, Joginia, FR9, K39, RP79-9, Sorhi, Anandi, CBF, Ramaniya	6	20
IR28, NDR119, Indrasan, Ratna, IR24, Improved Sona, Sarjoo 52, Dehula, Lalsar, Satha Opening, Anjani I, Padhini, T113, T132, Dulhiniya, T102, Agwar, Karhani (B), Garer, Bazarbhog, JBS1241, T128, T124, Bagari, Banshawa, Bilaspur, Carreon, Champa (F), Delha, Dadhaha, Dudiha, FRG4, FRG10, Jaisuria, Jalhar (C) 11, Kanga (Turahwa), KPW6B, Motibadam, Motipandey, MT4, NDR82, Pahuna, Soron, Sonachoor, Sumokhan, Tudat	7	46
Govind, NDR118, Kachni, Karanga, Tinpakhiyal, Dalkachari, Gajraj, Lakand, Bakaiya, Rohan 2662, Rambhog, Velluthacheera, Chinigurdi 11, Sapna, Sawani bhadaï, Selection-8, Lalki bhadaï, Lalkawa, Katki I, Katki II, Hari Nibbu, Culture 4, T136, Neebbu, Bagari (B), Karhani (R), Bhadaï (R), Babu Ram, NDR501, Pusa 33-18, T42, IR30, Ashahaniya, T-86, Kashi, T116, Kulsha, Motafarm, IR8	8	39
Rasi, Pusa 33, Cauvery, Saket 1, Saket 2, Saket 3, Jhona 349, N22, Madhuri, T21, Prasad, Kodaya, Kodya Improved, Culture 4 (RE), Karhan, Aktahwa (Red), Aktahwa (Black), Nootan, Dudhi, Champa fine, Ram Bilas, Bakain, Mungera, Sahdeyia, Rodola, Rohani, Reshma, Rajbhog, IET6663, Harikesh, Bhadaï (B), Bhadaï (W), Bala, Bakki, Singul, Satha Band (B), Satha Band (W), Parsom, Usha, T1242, T2, T46, KSR142, Bhunali, IET7301, Kota Basmati, T129, Gajgaur (B), Kapoorchini, Sarjoo 49, Anjana, Champa (C), Kalamdan, Mutra, Sukhawan, Talman, Tinpakhiya II, Akatahwa (FD), Gheebhat, Sath fine, Karnya, Kashi P. D., Katri III, Madhukar, NDR-49, Ramkajara, Rohan, Sawani, Akatahwa (T. D.), Anand, Basmati, Bindibali, Bindi kali, FH-109, Gajgaur, Gajgaur II (W), Jaya, Karanji, L. C. Pratapgarh, Madanchand, Mangova, Motifarm, Muskan, Nutex, Pasarhi, Safedawa, Sajna, Shyamghata, Sona, Turhawa, Lalka, T(N) 1.	9	92

^a Standard evaluation system for rice (1980).

Disease selection in rice in Colombia and Central America

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Materials are tested by CIAT for disease reaction prior to dispatch to national programs in Central America. Evaluations are done in Villavicencio, Colombia, a highly favorable disease

environment where blast (Bl) caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*, leaf scald (LSc) by *Gerlachia oryzae*, and brown spot (BS) by *Helminthosporium oryzae* are endemic.

We studied whether selecting under the high-disease environment prevalent in Villavicencio would predict disease performance in Central America, and compared the efficiency of this testing with selecting entries based only on Bl bed readings.

The analysis was based on disease

data reported from CIAT Rice Program evaluation plots in Villavicencio and from IRTTP collaborators in Central America who reported moderate to severe disease levels in 1982-86 for Bl and in 1985-86 for LSc and BS. Data for 1984 were not used because no disease evaluations from Colombia were available that year.

Each line was classified as selected for a given disease when it received a score lower than that of the nearest susceptible check in the field (*Standard evaluation system for rice*). The coincidence in selection between Colombia and Central America was estimated for each disease as the mean probability for a line to be selected in both locations.

The probability of coincidence in selection for Bl was 0.7 for 1982-83, when selection in Colombia was based on data from the uniform Bl bed in Palmira. It increased to 0.92 during 1985-86, when selection was based on field evaluations in Villavicencio. The predictability of selections done in Colombia for Central America for LSc and BS was calculated as 0.80 for 1985-86.

This indicates high similarity of the race distribution of Bl and the disease environment between Villavicencio, Colombia, and testing sites in Central America.

To estimate the consistency across time of disease evaluations done in Colombia, we calculated the probability of coincidence using 1985-86 data from observational nurseries planted in consecutive years in Colombia.

Probabilities of coincidence were 0.83 for Bl and 0.93 for LSc (see table). Coincidence for BS could not be estimated because incidence was low in 1986. No significant differences were observed between coincidence values of leaf Bl and LSc within years in Colombia and between Colombia and Central America for the period and genotypes considered.

We estimate that Bl and LSc evaluation in Villavicencio can predict reaction in Central America at least 80% of the time. Consistent BS evaluations might be very difficult to obtain. □

Probability of coincidence in disease selection for consecutive years in Colombia and between Colombia and Central America, 1985-86.^a

Disease	Colombia ^b	Central America	χ^2
Leaf blast	0.83	0.88	1.54 (0.1 < P < 0.9)
Leaf scald	0.93	0.85	2.75 (0.05 < P < 0.1)
Brown spot	–	0.79	–

^aProbability of coincidence: probability for a line to be selected in those locations in Central America with moderate to severe disease levels, given that it was selected in Colombia. ^bBS pressure was too low in 1986; thus no selection was made.

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Rice cultures with early plant resistance to bacterial blight (BB)

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BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye, a serious disease of wet season (1 Jun-30 Nov) rice in eastern Uttar Pradesh, is more damaging during the early crop season when temperature and atmospheric humidity are very high. Only the prebooting stage of long-duration varieties coincides with this period.

We tested a number of cultures for prebooting stage resistance to BB during 1986-87 wet season. Each entry was sown in two 2-m-long rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Plants were clip-inoculated with a suspension of a local BB isolate at tillering and rated at 15 d and 30 d after inoculation. TN1 at maximum tillering was the susceptible check.

Eight test cultures had disease scores of 2, 15 had scores of 3 (see table). □

Rice cultures showing early (prebooting stage) plant resistance to local BB pathogen isolate. Faizabad, U. P., India, 1986.

Variety or culture	Cross	Disease ^a score
RP1860-102-23-4-3	IET5656/Salamat	2
MTU7633	VasistalMahsuri	2
CR210-1018	Pankaj/Jagannath	2
CR98-7269	L. Z. Nira/TN1	2
CR260-131-5	CR151/CR1014	2
OR142-29	Pankaj/Sigadis	2
OR142-93	Pankaj/Sigadis	2
OR151-17	Hema/CR51-1523//Vikram	2
CR149-7171-271	MNP36/CR12//Pankaj	3
CR149-206	CR63-5218-1/Pankaj	3
CR98-8081	L. Z. Nira/TN1	3
MTU5182	MTU4569/ARC6650	3
CN836-3-6	–	3
CN836-3-8	–	3
CR376-KR-1	–	3
CR376-KR-2	–	3
CR376-KR-3	–	3
RAU83-8-4	BR-51-46-51/Mahsuri	3
RP1859-206-6-4-2-1	Swarnadhan/Benong III	3
RP1860-249-3-1-1	Swarnadhan/Salamat	3
RP1641-11-5-1-B	Vikram/Bulu Benong III	3
RP1641-44-7	–	3
RP1641-144-11-B	–	3
TN1 (check)	–	3

^aBased on *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1980).

Insect resistance

Gall midge (GM) resistance in traditional rice varieties in Bihar

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Seven local rice varieties collected from endemic GM areas of Chhotanagpur plateau, Bihar, were evaluated for resistance in 1984-86 wet seasons. Two resistant and one susceptible high-yielding varieties were included for

comparison. One-month-old seedlings were planted in 3- × 4-m plots with 3 replications. Silvershoot percentage was recorded at peak infestation (45 d after transplanting).

Local variety Baghpanjar consistently showed resistant reactions comparable to those of resistant checks RD202 and Shakti (Table 1). When 3-yr data were pooled, all varieties except Dhusri were better than Jaya. Baghpanjar matched the resistant checks. However, susceptible Jaya recorded the highest yield (Table 2). □

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